

Cutaneous Actinomycosis of Chest Wall in a Pediatric Patient Mimicking Ewing's Sarcoma on Radiological Images; A Case Report from Bahrain

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ABSTRACT

Primary cutaneous actinomycosis is a rare entity and the diagnosis requires a high index of suspicion. It is considered as a subacute to chronic bacterial infection caused by a filamentous gram-positive anaerobic to micro-aerophilic bacterium that is not acid fast. This infection occurs usually following a contaminated wound or foreign body trauma. We report a 13-year-old male patient, not known case of any medical illness, who presented with left side chest wall swelling, loss of appetite and loss of weight, for 4 months duration following a history of chest wall abrasions due to fall on the ground while running. Radiological images revealed large left lower chest wall mass involving soft tissue and rib bones suggestive of a malignant neoplasm along with left suprarenal region mass involving left infra-diaphragmatic lymph node suggestive of metastasis and two left lung nodules and left hilar lymph nodes enlargement suggestive of metastasis also. Histopathological examination of open biopsy specimen from the chest wall mass showed large basophilic filamentous bacterial aggregates (sulfur granules) surrounded by neutrophils, chronic inflammation and granulation tissue consistent with Actinomycosis. The patient was treated with intravenous antibiotics and showed dramatic improvement of the chest wall mass, suprarenal mass, lung nodules and the enlarged lymph nodes. We concluded that actinomycosis can be locally destructive and progress to generalize infections, causing complications and mimicking malignant neoplasms with risk of rupture, fistula formation, or spread to neighboring and distant organs and lymph nodes.

Keywords: Actinomycosis; Filamentous bacteria; Sarcoma; Cutaneous; Granulation tissue

INTRODUCTION

Actinomycosis is a rare invasive bacterial disease that causes a chronic, suppurative, granulomatous infection. *Actinomyces israelii* are the commonest species to cause disease. They are Gram-positive, anaerobic, filamentous bacilli that have low pathogenicity and normally colonize the mouth and gastrointestinal tract. However, they can be pathogenic in certain circumstances. This disease can affect multiple anatomical sites, being the cervicofacial presentation (60%) the most frequent,^[1] followed by the thoracic pulmonary (30%) and

abdominopelvic (20%).^[1] this infection can mimic neoplastic processes, and other suppurative infections. In consequence, the diagnosis of actinomycosis is challenging and the disease is frequently overlooked.

CASE PRESENTATION

On 12th February 2023, 13 year old male not known case of any medical illness, presented to our tertiary care hospital (Salmaniya Medical complex) outpatient pediatric surgery clinic with left side chest wall swelling for 4 months duration following a history of chest wall abrasions due to fall on the ground while running. With further history taking, the patient's parents stated that in November 2022 (nearly 4-5 months back) the patient had a fall on the ground and presented to accident and emergency department back then. X-ray was done and no future was identified. However, the chest wall swelling persisted and was accompanied by pain on and off. Moreover, he experienced loss of appetite and weight reduction. On physical examination, patient is afebrile complaining of left side chest wall heaviness and pain. He has a left side chest wall swelling extending from the left 6th intercostal space to the 12th intercostal space region. The skin surface shows abrasions with oozing pus and yellowish material. The patient's chest auscultation was not very remarkable. He had no abdominal distension, with soft abdomen and voluntary guarding and lower abdomen mild tenderness over the left iliac fossa. Physical examination of other systems was all within normal limits. He was admitted to the pediatric medical unit for a suspected malignant neoplasm for further investigation. Patient initial labs were as the following: WBC count ($8.62 \times 10^9/L$), RBC count ($4.69 \times 10^{12}/L$), Hemoglobin (11.1g/dL), NEUTROPHILS (70.5%), and NEUTROPHILS ABSOLUTE COUNT ($6.11 \times 10^9/L$), GLUCOSE (RANDOM) 5.5mmol/L, UREA 5 mmol/L, CREATININE 26.00 $\mu\text{mol}/L$, his electrolytes were within normal limits and his urine test was normal as well. His thyroid function tests, liver function tests, and bone profile were all within normal references. Patient was referred to pediatric medical care for further investigations. He was admitted to the pediatric ward and had a computed tomography studies for chest, abdomen and pelvis (Figure 1) and an abdominal and a pelvic ultrasound scan (Figure 2) the tests concluded that the patient has a large left lower chest wall mass measuring 8x4.4x11.8 cm in maximum diameter, extending from the 6th rib to the 12th rib and contains soft tissue and bony components highly suggestive of a sarcoma along with left suprarenal region mass like lesion measuring 4.4x3x6.7 cm which could be a left infra-diaphragmatic lymph node with metastasis as well as two left lung nodules and left hilar lymph nodes enlargements suggestive of metastasis also. The radiology doctors suggested a biopsy from the left chest wall mass for histopathology confirmation of the suspected diagnosis.

After that, the patient underwent an open biopsy for the main chest wall lesion and which was sent for histopathology examination.

Figure. 1 Computed tomography studies for chest showing a large, irregular chest wall mass involving soft tissue and bone (red arrow).

Figure. 2. Ultrasonography scans of pelvis showing a large left suprarenal mass with a well-defined outlining (yellow line).

Histological and immunohistochemistry methods and Morphometrical assay

The histological diagnosis was made on hematoxylineosin- stained slides along with Periodic acid–Schiff (PAS) stained section, Silver stained (GMS) section and Acid fast (Z-N) stained section. Sections of the sampled tissue were evaluated through light microscopy (Olympus, CX41).

Histological findings

Gross examination of the specimen reveals multiple fragments of tan soft tissue with friable texture, the largest piece measuring 1.5x1x0.5 cm. The outer surface looks soft with focal necrosis. No skin surface was identified. Microscopic examination of the submitted tissue sections which are hematoxylin-eosin-stained slides (Figure 3.A and B) display presence of sulfur granules and filamentous, Gram-positive rod-shaped bacteria surrounded by

mixed inflammation. These bacterial colonies were positive for Periodic acid–Schiff (PAS) stain and silver stain (GMS) (Figure 3C and D). However, they were negative for acid fast stain (ZN) (Figure 3.E).

Tissue cultures for bacteria, fungus, and mycobacteria were negative.

Figure. 3. A. H&E stained section shows large basophilic filamentous bacterial aggregates (sulfur granules) surrounded by neutrophils, chronic inflammation and granulation tissue (Magnification $\times 10/0.08$ NA). B. H&E stained section shows large basophilic filamentous bacterial aggregates (sulfur granules) surrounded by neutrophils, chronic inflammation and granulation tissue (Magnification $\times 40/0.40$ NA). C. Periodic acid–Schiff (PAS) stained section shows positive staining of Actinomyces colonies (Dark purple) (Magnification $\times 20/0.40$ NA). D. Silver stained (GMS) section shows positive staining of Actinomyces colonies (Black) (Magnification $\times 20/0.40$ NA). E. Acid fast (ZN) stained section shows negative staining of Actinomyces colonies (Red arrow) (magnification $\times 20/0.08$ NA).

Clinical follow up

After the diagnosis of actinomycosis was made, the patient was treated with intravenous antibiotics along with oral antibiotics as maintenance. He completed 6-week course of antibiotic treatment and experienced dramatic improvement for the chest wall mass, suprarenal mass and lung nodules. The lesions were proven by radiological assessment of the patient. Hence, he underwent a repeated Pan-CT (Computed tomography) studies which confirm the reduction of the sizes of all the previously mentioned lesions.

DISCUSSION

Actinomycosis is a rare chronic disease caused by *Actinomyces* spp., anaerobic Gram-positive, filamentous bacteria that normally colonize the human mouth and digestive and genital tracts. However, it can be pathogenic in certain conditions with the presence of low oxygen and mucosal lesions like in female patients with intrauterine contraceptive devices (IUCD) or in immune-compromised patients with infected skin wounds.^[1] Primary cutaneous pulmonary actinomycosis is a rare but important and challenging diagnosis to make especially in pediatric age group. It requires a high index of suspicion along with a competent history of trauma such as abrasions or wounds. Even when the clinical suspicion is high, the disease is commonly confused with other chronic suppurative skin diseases, internal organs suppurative infections and with various organs malignancies.

[1]

Cutaneous actinomycosis occurs at all ages, although it is very unusual in children. A bimodal age distribution with an earlier peak at ages 11–20 has been described, but most series describe a clear peak incidence in the 4th and 5th decades.^[2]

The mechanism of colonization of the pathogen, *Actinomyces israelii*, the primary pathogen to cause cutaneous actinomycosis is not fully understood. However, it is attributed to either post-traumatic exposure or direct implantation of the pathogen via animal, insects or human bites.^[2] Relating the history of our patient to the fact that he had a fall on the ground with subsequent abrasions of the skin of the chest wall can justify the presence of this infection albeit the rarity of occurrence in immune-competent children.

Actinomycosis may mimic many conditions like neoplastic processes, tuberculosis, and nocardiosis in various anatomical sites.^[3] The distinction between these conditions are based on clinico-radiological and pathological correlations. In our case, the radiological features of the chest wall mass which was extending from the skin, subcutaneous soft tissue and up to the underlying ribs along with multiple lung nodules and left suprarenal mass gave the impression of an infiltrative malignant neoplasm with metastasis. Because the patient is a child, a provisional diagnosis of Ewing's sarcoma was made. The history was very much going with the suspicion of malignancy as the patient complained of loss of appetite, loss of weight and general tiredness. Hence, a biopsy was indicated to confirm the clinical suspicions.

The diagnosis of actinomycosis is made by a positive culture or the visualization of necrosis with sulfur granules and Gram-positive filamentous bacterial colonies in the histopathology study.^[4]

A close differential diagnosis to actinomycosis is nocardiosis. *Actinomyces* and *Nocardia* are two different genera of bacteria. While they are both Gram-positive bacteria, they have distinct morphological, biochemical, and ecological characteristics.^[5] The most notable difference between the two is the way they form their filaments. *Actinomyces* are branched, forming a network of delicate filaments, while *Nocardia* form straight filaments.^[5] To differentiate between them in histological sections, a set of special stains is usually ordered. *Actinomyces* are positive for Periodic acid–Schiff (PAS) stain and silver stain (GMS) while they are negative for Acid fast stain (ZN). On the other hand, *Nocardia* is positive for Silver stain (GMS) and modified acid fast stains.^[6,7]

Management plan for patients with actinomycosis require high doses of penicillin's G or amoxicillin for long periods of time (6–12 months), but the duration of antimicrobial therapy could be reduced to 3 months in patients with total surgical resection.^[8] A dramatic response will be noticed on the mass-like lesions locally and systemically following the administration of the antibiotics. However, some conditions may have less response and requires further investigations and follow up to rule out the possibility of the presence of second undiagnosed pathology.^[9]

CONCLUSIONS

Due to its rarity, cutaneous actinomycosis continue to be challenging for radiologist, pathologist and surgeons. It can be locally destructive and progress to generalize systemic infection, causing complications and mimicking malignant neoplasms with risk of rupture, fistula formation, or spread to neighboring and distant organs and lymph nodes. However, in the era of minimally invasive diagnostic approaches, a biopsy can help ascertain diagnosis (as in our case) and further guide management, primarily long-term antibiotics, and debridement of infected tissue. Prognosis is excellent in healthy patients with the prompt management. We finally recommend all physicians to keep actinomycosis in differential diagnoses of suspected chest wall and abdominal malignancies.^[10]

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